

Notes

Alkali Metal Complexes. Mixed Ligand Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of some Organic Acids with 8-Hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide

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IN continuation of our previous work¹⁻³, a number of mixed ligand complexes of alkali metal salts with 8-hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide of the general formula ML.HL', where M=Li, Na or K; L=deprotonated salicylic acid, anthranilic acid, *o*-nitrophenol or 1-nitroso-2-naphthol; HL'=8-hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide, have been obtained.

Experimental

The ligand 8-hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide prepared by the method reported in literature⁴, m.p. 139°, was found identical with that reported^{4,5}.

An equimolar mixture of the alkali metal salt (ML) and 8-hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide (HL') in absolute ethanol was refluxed for 15-30 min with continuous stirring. The clear solution was concentrated and cooled, when the adducts separated out. The adducts were filtered, washed with absolute ethanol and then dried in an electric oven at 80°. Adducts of lithium salicylate, potassium salicylate and sodium 1-nitroso-2-naphtholate did not separate out.

Results and Discussion

Physical and analytical data of the ligand and the complexes are listed in Table 1.

The complexes are stable in dry air, but decompose rapidly on exposure to air giving dark brown solids of indeterminate composition. They are soluble in most polar solvents with dissociation, but are insoluble in non-polar solvents, such as benzene, toluene and diethyl ether.

The strong intensity ir bands (Table 2) present in 8-hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide at ~1 525, 1 270 and 880 cm⁻¹ can be ascribed to the phenolic OH deformation modes coupled with the C-O stretching modes ($\delta_{OO} + \delta_{OH}$) and to the out-of-plane deformation vibration, respectively⁶. On complexation, the band at 1 525 cm⁻¹ undergoes a negative shift of 5-33 cm⁻¹. In case of the complex of lithium anthranilate, this band appears as split bands at 1 498 and 1 490 cm⁻¹. The band at 1 270 cm⁻¹, present in 8-hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide, suffers a negative shift of 10-20 cm⁻¹ on complexation. Similarly, in complexes, the band at 880 cm⁻¹ of the ligand shifted to lower frequencies by 5-20 cm⁻¹. These features, alongwith the disappearance of the multiple medium strong bands over a wide range^{6,7} 2 850-1 750 cm⁻¹, are indicative of the coordination of the ligand HL' through oxygen atom of the hydroxyl moiety. Free ligand exhibits the N-O stretching frequency at ~1 320 cm⁻¹ and the N-O band (coupled probably with OH bending modes)^{6,7} at 820 cm⁻¹. In the spectra of the complexes, the N-O stretching frequency shifted to lower frequencies by 5-25 cm⁻¹. The

TABLE-1 ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	M.p. °C	$\Delta\mu$ Ω ⁻¹ cm mol ⁻¹	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
				N	M
NaSalA.HL'	Yellow	170	4.0	4.23 (4.36)	7.40 (7.16)
LiAnc.HL'	Cream	198d	2.5	9.00 (9.21)	-
NaAnc.HL'	Cream	170d	3.0	8.65 (8.75)	7.50 (7.18)
KAnc.HL'	Cream	155d	6.0	8.53 (8.33)	11.55 (11.60)
LiONP.HL'	Pale yellow	210d	1.5	9.01 (9.15)	-
NaONP.HL' ^a	Yellow	150d	4.0	- (8.70)	7.25 (7.14)
KONP.HL'	Greenish yellow	125	7.5	8.18 (8.28)	11.60 (11.54)
Li1N2N.HL'	Brown	115d	1.5	8.54 (8.23)	-
K1N2N.HL'	Brown	200d	5.0	7.50 (7.53)	10.60 (10.48)

*HL' = 8-hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide, SalA = salicylic acid, Anc = anthranilic acid, ONP = *o*-nitrophenol, 1N2N = 1-nitroso-2-naphthol. ^aExploded during combustion for estimating N.

TABLE 2—SELECTED IR BANDS (cm⁻¹)*

Compd **	O-H...O	CO+OH	NO	NO	Additional bands
HL'	2 800-1 750v	1 525s, 1 270s, 880s	1 320s	820s	-
NaSalA HL'	2 3°O 2 34, 1 900br	1 492s, 1 260s, 868s	1 308s	815s	708s
LiAnc HL'	1 900br	1 498sh, 1 250sh, 860s, 1 490s	1 310m	815s	700s
NaAnc HL'	2 350-2 28, 1 900br	1 500s, 1 260s 865s	1 305m	815s	690s
KAnc.HL'	2 350br	1 520m, 1 255s, 865s	1 315s	812s	718m
Li1N2N.HL'	2 350br	1 525m, 1 280s, 875w	1 215m	820s	728sh
K1N2N.HL'	2 350br	1 525s, 1 270s, 870m	1 305w	820s	728vw

*v = variable bands, vw = very weak, s = strong, sh = shoulder

**Explanation as in Table 1.

N-O bending mode too shifted to lower frequencies by 5-10 cm⁻¹. These features suggest coordination of the ligand through the oxygen atom of the N-O moiety. A new broad band of weak to medium intensity in the region 2 400-1 900 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes, which could be attributed to O-H...O absorption, suggests the hydrogen bonding to be an essential feature of these complexes.

Molar conductivities were measured in DMF at 23° at a concentration of 10⁻³M. A value of ca 35-40 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ is indicative of a 1:1 electrolyte⁹. None of the complexes approach molar conductance value for 1:1 electrolyte. The slightly higher values for the potassium complexes imply that they have undergone partial dissociation in the solvent used.

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Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II) Benzilates with Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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THE present paper reports the complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} benzilate with *N*-base quinoline and β -picoline in continuation of our previous works¹⁻³

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Aqueous solution of metal (Cu, Ni, Zn, Co) salts were mixed separately with alcoholic solution of benzoic acid when metal benzilates were precipitated, which were filtered under suction, washed with small quantity of alcohol followed by ether and dried in vacuum.

Metal benzilates were refluxed with quinoline and β -picoline separately in ethanol medium for 0.5 h. The volume of the solution was reduced to 5 ml by a rotary vacuum evaporator and kept overnight. The crystalline compounds that separated out were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol and ether, and dried in vacuum desiccator. Metal and nitrogen were estimated by standard methods. Analytical data of the complexes were presented in Table 1.